

A Simple Proof of the Euler Infinite Product for the Riemann Zeta Function

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Abstract: Nowadays, the growing complexity of mathematical and computational modelling demands the simplicity of mathematical equations for solving today's scientific problems and challenges. In this article, the author provides a simple proof of the Euler product for the Riemann zeta function.

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1. Introduction

The Riemann zeta function [1, 2] is an important special function in analytic number theory and has applications in physics, probability theory, and statistics. The following function denotes the Riemann zeta function.

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + 5^{-s} + \dots, \quad \forall \operatorname{Re}(s) > 1. \quad (1)$$

2. Euler Product for Riemann Zeta Function

The following expression represents the Euler product for the Riemann zeta function [1, 2].

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \prod_{p \text{ Prime}} (1 - p^{-s})^{-1}, \quad \forall \operatorname{Re}(s) > 1. \quad (2)$$

The equation (2) is rewritten as follows:

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right], \text{ where } p_i \text{ is } i^{\text{th}} \text{ prime.}$$

Let us prove the Euler product for the Riemann zeta function.

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right] = \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_1^s}} \right] \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_2^s}} \right] \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_3^s}} \right] \dots \quad (3)$$

Each item denotes a geometric series [3-37] in the above infinite product (Euler product).

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right] = \left[\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_1^{is}} \right] \left[\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_2^{is}} \right] \left[\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p_3^{is}} \right] \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right] = \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_1^s} + \frac{1}{p_1^{2s}} + \frac{1}{p_1^{3s}} + \dots \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_2^s} + \frac{1}{p_2^{2s}} + \frac{1}{p_2^{3s}} + \dots \right) \dots \quad (5)$$

By simplifying the infinite product, we obtain

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right] = 1 + \sum_{1 \leq i} \frac{1}{p_i^s} + \sum_{1 \leq i < j} \frac{1}{p_i^s p_j^s} + \sum_{1 \leq i < j < k} \frac{1}{p_i^s p_j^s p_k^s} + \dots \quad (6)$$

By rearranging the expression (6) in order, we get

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right] = 1 + \frac{1}{p_1^s} + \frac{1}{p_2^s} + \frac{1}{p_1^s p_1^s} + \frac{1}{p_3^s} + \frac{1}{p_1^s p_2^s} + \frac{1}{p_4^s} + \frac{1}{p_1^s p_1^s p_1^s} + \frac{1}{p_2^s p_2^s} + \dots \quad (7)$$

Here, $p_1^s = 2^s, p_2^s = 3^s, p_3^s = 5^s, p_4^s = 7^s, p_5^s = 11^s, p_6^s = 13^s, \dots$

$$\prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_i^s}} \right] = 1 + \frac{1}{2^s} + \frac{1}{3^s} + \frac{1}{4^s} + \frac{1}{5^s} + \frac{1}{6^s} + \frac{1}{7^s} + \frac{1}{8^s} + \frac{1}{9^s} + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s}. \quad (8)$$

$$\text{For instance, } \frac{1}{p_1^s p_2^s p_3^s} = \frac{1}{2^s 3^s 5^s} = \frac{1}{(2 \times 3 \times 5)^s} = \frac{1}{30^s}.$$

From the expression (8), we conclude that

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{p_k^s}} \Rightarrow \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-s} = \prod_{p \text{ Prime}} (1 - p^{-s})^{-1}, \quad \forall \text{Re}(s) > 1.$$

This final expression represents the Euler product for the Reimann zeta function.

3. Conclusion

In the article, the author has provided a simple proof of the Euler infinite product for the Riemann zeta function. The Riemann zeta function is used as an application in physics, probability theory, and statistics. The following function denotes the Riemann zeta function.

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